

Politeness strategies employed by an English teacher in “*Program Kelas Full Day Sains dan Bahasa*” at MTs Mathalibul Huda

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- Abstract : This study focused on the politeness strategy used by an English teacher in the “Kelas Full Day Sains dan Bahasa Program” at MTs Mathalibul Huda. The aim was to analyze the types of politeness strategy and the dominant strategy in classroom interaction. The method of this study was a qualitative descriptive approach. Brown and Levinson's (1978) theory was chosen by researchers to analyze the types of politeness strategies. The data collection techniques were observing, recording, transcribing, checking the transcription and selecting the speaker's utterances. Data analysis involved identifying utterances based on the politeness strategies used, analyzing frequency, interpreting data, and drawing conclusions. There were four types of politeness strategies: blunt politeness, positive politeness, negative politeness, and confidential politeness. The result of four meetings revealed that 42 out of 103 daters had a politeness strategy of 41% classified as “overt politeness,” 39 out of 103 daters had a positive politeness rate of 38%, and 16 out of 103 daters had a negative politeness strategy of 15 were categorized as % and 6 of 103 data were categorized as off-record of 6%. Therefore, the predominant type of politeness strategy used by English teachers in teaching and learning is direct openness. This indicates that the teacher valued concise directness in his statements.
- Keywords : *politeness strategy, MTs Mathalibul Huda Mlonggo Jepara, Program Kelas Full Day Sains Dan Bahasa*
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INTRODUCTION

For humans to interact and acquire information, communication is a necessary component. Through communication, addressers exchange thoughts and emotions in order to encode messages (Rosdiana, 2016). People use politeness techniques in their daily interactions as a way to demonstrate proper speech acts (Purwanto, 2020). As part of the politeness strategy, etiquette is a good habit to uphold and is represented in communication about socially acceptable universal ideas. Instead of using the Russian term for speech etiquette, English researchers use the term politeness. In diverse cultural contexts, they use verbal language to convey their communication in unique ways (Rosdiana and Candraloka, 2023). A politeness strategy becomes a means of engagement in certain communicative events. It strengthens relationships, increases confidence and self-worth, and enhances communication abilities (Borris & Zecho, 2018).

Politeness strategies, which are a subset of pragmatics, use the "say something or say nothing" communication strategy to address how people express their feelings and thoughts through their words. Finding the meaning behind a speaker's words in a given context is just as important as understanding the words themselves (Yule, 2006). Brown-Levinson popularized the idea of using politeness as a strategy to maintain a positive self-image and to be amiable (Cutting, 2002). Sometimes people behave rudely toward others for various reasons. The purpose of this study was to examine how English teachers applied the four politeness strategies described in Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory, as well as the dominant strategy employed in classroom interactions. As a professional educator, developing relationships is essential to determining the right words to use and the proper level of etiquette to use (Seken, 2011). Therefore, determining the social status of the addressee, establishing a social distance, and estimating the degree of authority held by the addressee are necessary to determine the appropriate level of politeness to use in communication without upsetting the addressee. The four politeness strategies theory by Brown and Levinson (1987) was applied in this study as a qualitative research method using a descriptive approach (Brown and Levinson, 1987).

Research on politeness tactics used in spoken contexts, like presidential debates, has attracted a lot of interest (Batubara et al. , 2022), on social media (Shalihah and Winarsih, 2023), and on comedy shows (Hutahaean et al. (2021). Different strategies are used in different contexts for communication competence, particularly when it comes to teacher-led communication in the classroom. Two skills that educators need to master are competency and skill (Santosa et al. , 2022) and the ability to communicate (Jailmilah et al. (2017) in a balanced frequency manner. For the purpose of fostering communication and bringing life to the classroom, teachers should possess pedagogical competence. As a result, teachers' effective communication strategies become part of their classroom management. The teacher-led classroom politeness strategy discussion garnered interest from multiple researchers, who looked into the politeness strategy used by teachers and students in the classroom (Ginting & Pasaribu, 2023; Fitriyani & Andriyanti, 2020). A number of other researchers looked into teacher-implemented politeness strategies (Dewi et al. 2023) as well as a lecturer (Aeni, 2019). The researcher examined teachers' politeness strategy as the focus of this study because the teacher's role in classroom management was crucial to the lively interaction between teacher and students in the classroom. Previous research used Geoffrey Leech's (2016) theory to analyze the maxims demonstrated by EFL teachers and the impact on students. Although the other researchers used Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory, the influencing factors could not be clearly explained. The novelty of this research is that it uses Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory as a politeness strategy and explains the influencing factors of teachers producing language in the classroom. It is interesting to discuss how important the teacher's role in

maintaining classroom interaction is to build a good relationship between teacher and students and also achieve effective learning.

Politeness has become an essential part of interactions between people. Mills (2003) states that politeness, as part of pragmatics, is a way people show respect to other people and avoid insults without hurting others by taking into account the situation they are speaking to (Dewanti, 2022). According to Leech (1983) and Brown and Levinson (1987), politeness is influenced by various factors, including social distance, social status, and gender, with the aim of showing respect and saving face (Purwanto & Soepriatmadji, 2013). The four politeness strategies carried out using Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory are the blunt politeness strategy, the positive politeness strategy, the negative politeness strategy, and the intimate politeness strategy (Brown & Levinson, 1987). The politeness strategies that speakers use to achieve specific goals in social relationships, according to Brown and Levinson (1987), are face-threatening act (FTA), public self-image, and sense of self (Marpudianto, 2020).

METHOD

The qualitative research feature is a key tool in seeking answers to research questions on politeness strategy conducted on MTs by Grade 8F2 English teachers in the “Program Kelas Full Day Sains dan Bahasa” at Mathalibul Huda Mlonggo, Jepara. The prevailing politeness strategy is carried out (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). Techniques for collecting data consisted of observing and listening to conversations, recording, transcribing, checking the transcription, and selecting the speaker's utterances. Data analysis included identifying utterances, classifying utterances using politeness strategies, analyzing frequency, interpreting data and drawing conclusions in “Program Kelas Full Day Sains dan Bahasa” at MTs. Mathalibul Huda Mlonggo in January 2024. This research took place in four sessions and each session lasted about 60 minutes. When analyzing the data, the researchers transcribed the entire interaction from the video recording. After the teacher's transcribed interaction, the researchers coded and classified the types of politeness strategies based on Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory and counted the total of each of them. In the final step, the researchers identified the predominant types of politeness strategy and analyzed the results using qualitative descriptive analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research conducted to investigate the teacher's politeness strategy in classroom interaction. This classroom observation conducted in four meetings in 1st semester of grade 9F2 at Program Full Day Sains dan Bahasa in MTs Mathalibul Huda. The researchers used video recording to record the whole of teaching learning process to investigate politeness strategy used. The first kind of politeness strategy is bald-on-record. Bald on record happened in spontaneous condition, such as in emergency condition, giving instruction, and sometimes interlocutor have a close relationship with the hearer. Secondly is positive politeness. It occurred when interlocutor making a joke, giving promise, optimistic, notice, attend to the hearer, etc. The third is negative politeness. Lastly is off record. Off-record politeness strategy occurred when interlocutor gives a hint or sarcastic to the hearer. This result of this research explained below:

1. Meeting One

In first meeting, the teacher thought simple presents tense, specifically about adding ‘s’ and ‘es’ to verb. The researchers found 22 utterances that classified on politeness strategy used by teacher in the class as follows:

a. **Bald-on-Record politeness strategy**

“ditulisnya nanti saja.”

(Write it later.)

Based on that utterance, the teacher gave an instruction to the students to stop writing the materials first because the teacher want the students pay attention to his explanation. It means, the teacher has higher power of the students.

“Close the door, please!”

In this utterance, the teacher asked student to close the door because the teacher feels dazzled. So, in this utterance the teacher used bald on record.

b. **Positive politeness strategy**

“How are you? Are you in a good condition?”

In that utterance, the teacher used politeness strategy because the teacher gave respect to the students by asking student’s condition.

“Kelihatan tidak? Mana yang susah ini? Yang tidak tahu artinya?”

(Can you see that? Is there any difficulty? Do you know the meaning?)

Based on the utterance, the teacher noticed the students that perhaps they cannot watch the screen clearly and do not know the meaning of vocabularies.

*“City ini berarti kota yaa, bukan nama orang” *jokingly*

(‘city’ means *kota*, right? it’s not the name of someone)

In this utterance, the teacher used positive politeness because the teacher tried to make a joke by saying that the meaning of ‘city’ is *kota*, not the name of person. However, in Javanese there is a lot of people with the name ‘*siti*’, so it has similar pronounce with ‘city’.

“Jangan lupa verbnya, kalau subjectnya menunjukkan diganti berarti verbnya harus diganti.”

(Notice to the verb. If the subject is changed, so the verb must be changed)

The teacher reminds the students to read the question. However, the teacher noticed to the student’s answer when he saw the students one by one. It means, this utterance classified in positive politeness.

c. **Negative politeness**

“Siapa namanya? Hafiz?”

(What is his name? Hafiz?)

The teacher asked the name of the student when he asked that student to answer his question. This utterance classified in negative politeness because of questioning the name of the student.

2. Meeting Two

In second meeting, the materials that explained of the teacher is present continuous. Moreover, the researchers found 25 utterances of the teacher that used some kinds of politeness strategy. Some of the utterances described below:

a. Bald-on-record politeness strategy

“Itu mainannya disimpen aja. Disimpen yaa.”

(Save those toys. Save it)

The teacher asked students to save their game. It is because when the teacher explained the material some of students enjoy to play game. So, the utterance that used of the teacher is bald-on-record.

“I give 10 minutes for each group.”

The teacher gave an instruction to the students that the times to discuss is about 10 minutes. It means, in this utterance the teacher has a higher power that students to manage the discussion. Because of that, the researchers classified this utterance in bald on record.

b. Positive politeness strategy

“Nava, kenapa Nava? Kepalanya diangkat”

(Nava, why Nava? Rise your head, please.)

In this utterance, the teacher noticed to one of the students to put his head on the table when the teacher explained the material. However, the teacher asked him to rise his head and listen to the teacher explanation. So, notice to the hearer is one of characteristics of positive politeness.

“Semoga apa yang kita pelajari bermanfaat. Don’t forget to study, don’t play mobile game too much, okey? Just balance between study and play mobile game.”

(Hopefully, what we have learned today is useful for us. Don’t forget to study, don’t play mobile game too much, okey? Just balance between study and play mobile game.)

The teacher used positive politeness because in the last meeting the teacher prays for the students and give the advice to balance between study and playing mobile legend.

c. Negative politeness strategy

“Mungkin ga kalian waktu liburan belajar?”

(is it possible that you will study on the holiday?)

In this utterance, the teacher had curiosity about students’ study habit during holiday. So, he showed his pessimistic toward his students from his saying. It indicates that his utterance shows negative politeness.

d. Off-record politeness strategy

“Silau ya. (look at the door)”

(Dazzling, aren’t you?)

This utterance, the teacher gave a hint to the students that the door is open and it made dazzling. So, the teacher wanted to ask the students to close the door by do not saying specifically. Therefore, this utterance called off record.

3. Meeting Three

In the meeting three, the discussion was conducted. They discussed about the second meeting's assignment. The material was about the application of present continuous tense in sentences. In this meeting, the researchers found 31 utterances that included in politeness strategy. The kinds of politeness described below:

a. Bald-on-record politeness strategy

“Silahkan tugasnya dikeluarkan yang kemarin. Silahkan bergabung sama kelompok kalian masing-masing.”

(Please, show your last meeting assignment. Go with your group.)

This utterance, the teacher gives an instruction to the students to open their assignment in the last meeting.

“Please pay attention to the last presentation.”

In this utterance, the teacher asked students to pay attention to their friend that present the discussion. Because in that time, the students just talk to their friends and did not listen to the presenters. So, this utterance that used by the teacher is bald on record.

b. Positive politeness

“Who did not come in the previous meeting? *Siapa yang ga berangkat?* (who is absent today?) *Ada 4-5 orang* (there are 4-5 people altogether).”

The teacher asked to the students about who did not come in the previous meeting. It is because not only one student is absent from the class, but there are 4 until 5 students who are absent from the class in previous meeting. So, in this utterance the teacher notice that students who are absent in previous meeting come to the class. It means, this utterance included in positive politeness.

“Itu contoh dari kalimat yang negative. Ok, itu sebagai pemantapan kalian untuk menganalisa kalimat present continuous yang ada dalam teks ini, paham? Silakan temannya dibantu yaa, ok dilanjutkan.”

(That is the example of negative sentence. Well, that's to corroborate your analysis of present continuous sentence in this text. Is that clear? Please, do cooperate!)

In this utterance, the teacher gave reason why the teacher repeated his explanation. It is because the teacher wants to remind the students about the materials before they continue their discussion in analyzing present continuous on the text in the last meeting.

c. Negative politeness strategy

“Tidak ada yang nulis kemarin?”

(Nobody wrote the materials in the last meeting?)

This utterance explains that the teacher questioning about what is the students write in last meeting? Is it really there is nobody write the materials? Therefore this utterance included in negative politeness.

d. Off-record politeness strategy

“Papan tulisnya penuh banget yaa.”

(The white board is full.)

The teacher gave a hint to the students that the white board is full. It means, the teacher wants to ask student to clean the white board without give the instruction directly. Therefore, this utterance included in off record.

“Terus besok bawa hp lagi yaa”

(bring your cell phone again)

In this time, the student told to the teacher that he brought his phone to the school, then his phone confiscated by the teacher because there is a rule that the students are not allowed to take handphone to the school. Therefore, in this utterance the teacher used sarcastic word to the student to bring his phone again when the phone is new.

4. Meeting Four

In the last meeting, the teacher still teach present continuous tense, specifically is about verbs that cannot be added with ‘ing’ in present continuous. The researchers found 25 utterances that included in politeness strategy. Then, some kinds of politeness strategy that found by the researchers described below:

a. Bald-on-record politeness strategy

“Satria, listen to me.”

The teacher asked Satria to listen to him because Satria do not focus on teacher explanation and keep talking to his friend. Thus, the utterance that used by the teacher is bald on record.

b. Positive politeness strategy

“Where is the remote? Remote nya ga ada ya?”

(Where is the remote? Is the remote lost?)

In this utterance, the teacher has a close relationship with the students. So, the teacher makes sure that the remote was lost or how.

c. Negative politeness strategy

“Iya kalau inget ga usah. Tapi kan kalian ga inget sih?”

(If you remember, do not (write). But you do not remember, right?)

The teacher did pessimistic in this utterance. It is because when the students asked the material is should to write by the students or not, but the teacher said that he’s believed that the students do not remember the material that’s been studies. Therefore this utterance is included negative politeness.

“Ga boleh pulang dulu, itu namanya korupsi.”

(Don’t leave. It is called corruption.)

The teacher normalized that going home first is a corruption of time.

d. Off-record politeness strategy

“Biasanya kalau yang kayak gini, buat pengakuan gitu dia yang melakukan”

(Usually, if this is the one who makes the teacher confession, it’s him.)

In this utterance, the teacher did sarcastic to the students that the student has ever do bullying. So, this utterance that used is included off record.

Based on the observation it can be drawn a data analysis of politeness strategy used by English teacher as follows:

Kinds of politeness	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Frequency
	Meetings				
Bald on record	10	12	13	7	42
Positive politeness	10	8	9	12	39
Negative politeness	2	4	5	5	16
Off record	0	1	4	1	6
Total					103

Figure 1. Table frequency in 4 meetings

It can be concluded the dominant types of politeness strategy that used by the teacher on diagram below:

Figure 2. diagram frequency of politeness strategy used

From table above, it can be known that the most dominant types of politeness strategy that used by the teacher in teaching learning process is bald on record, positive politeness, negative politeness, and off record.

CONCLUSION

After searching and analyzing the politeness strategy carried out by English teachers in the “Kelas Full Day Sains dan Bahasa Program” (in the Science and Language Full Day Course Program) at MTs Mathalibul Huda Mlonggo Jepara, it was found that there are 103 data of it Politeness strategies representing positive, blunt, negative, and confidential politeness strategies were discovered in four meetings in January 2004. Specifically, they included 42 of 103 data. 41% and 39% of the data were categorized as blunt politeness strategy. Out of 103 data, 38% were categorized as positive politeness strategy, 16 out of 103 data were categorized as negative politeness strategy of 15% and 6 out of 103 data were categorized as unobserved politeness strategy of 6%. Furthermore, the predominant politeness strategy is the strategy of blunt politeness. This indicates that the teacher emphasized the use of a straightforward form when the speaker produced direct, clear, and concise speech when communicating with characters.

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